

Kinetic spectrophotometric determination of an important pharmaceutical compound, α -Methyldopa

S. Muzaffar Ali Andrabi^{a*}, Shabeela Aziz^b and Raafia Najam^b

^aUniversity Science Instrumentation Centre, ^bP.G. Department of Chemistry,

University of Kashmir, Srinagar-190 006, Jammu and Kashmir, India

^aE-mail : muzaffar2000@gmail.com Fax : 91-194-2421357

Manuscript received 12 July 2011, revised 12 October 2011, accepted 13 October 2011

Abstract : A simple, economical and accurate kinetic spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of α -Methyldopa in pure and pharmaceutical preparations. The method is based on the reaction of the drug with sodium carbonate in aqueous medium. The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically by measuring the increase in absorbance with time at 440 nm. The initial rate method, fixed absorbance method and fixed time method were used for constructing the calibration graph. Calibration graphs are linear over the concentration range of 25–300 ppm. The method has been successfully applied to the determination of α -Methyldopa in pure and in pharmaceutical formulations. The method offers the advantages of simplicity, rapidity, reproducibility and cost effectivity.

Keywords : Determination, spectrophotometric, α -Methyldopa, kinetic, sodium carbonate.

Introduction

α -Methyldopa [3-hydroxy- α -methyl-L-tyrosine or 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-methylalanine] is an important pharmaceutical compound used in treating hypertension since the original publication of Oates *et al.* in 1960¹. It is a catechol derivative (catecholamine) and acts as aminocarboxylase inhibitor. The widespread use of this drug has promoted many researchers to develop sensitive and accurate analytical methods for its determination, especially for the routine quality control analysis of pharmaceutical products. Various analytical methods are now available for the determination of catechol derivatives in pharmaceutical preparations and biological fluids. These methods involve the use of gas and liquid chromatography²⁻⁷, titrimetry⁸⁻¹³, potentiometry¹⁴, voltammetry¹⁵, amperometry¹⁶ and electrocatalysis¹⁷. Some of these methods require sophisticated and/or expensive instruments and some require tedious procedures with rigorous control of the experimental conditions. Some of the titrimetric methods require non-aqueous solvents⁸ while others⁹⁻¹³ are indirect titrations based on reduction reactions which are susceptible to interferences by unsaturated organic compounds. Since the spectrophotometric determinations offer significant economic advantages over chro-

matographic and other methods and are easily manageable by third world countries, many spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the determination of catecholamine derivatives including α -Methyldopa¹⁸⁻³⁴. However most of the spectrophotometric methods for the assay of physiologically active catecholamine derivatives like levodopa, methyldopa, dopamine hydrochloride and pyrocatechol, in general, suffer from limitations²², Ribeiro *et al.*³⁴ have also summarized the limitations of these spectrophotometric methods as follows : "Most of these methods suffer from several disadvantages such as the need of the long waiting times¹⁹⁻²⁴ or heating step²³⁻²⁵ for the reaction development, instability of the coloured species²⁶, complex procedure²⁷, require non-aqueous media^{28,29}, narrow linear range³³ or have not been applied to pharmaceutical formulations³¹.

In the present communication a simple, rapid, economical and accurate kinetic spectrophotometric method is proposed for the determination of α -Methyldopa in pure and pharmaceutical preparations. The method is based on the reaction of α -Methyldopa with sodium carbonate in water at room temperature. The method involves a one step reaction, does not involve any extraction or heating steps and does not show any interferences from excipi-

ents normally found with methyl dopa in pharmaceutical preparation. The reaction is monitored spectrophotometrically, and the change in absorbance with time is measured at 440 nm.

Experimental

α -Methyl dopa a GR grade chemical obtained from Sigma (USA) and sodium carbonate (AR grade) was procured from Qualigens, Fine Chemicals, Glaxo, India. Double distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions. Standard solution of α -Methyl dopa was prepared daily by dissolving 100 mg in 10 ml water and further diluted to working concentration range. α -Methyl dopa is slowly soluble in water and its solutions were prepared in freshly boiled and cooled water to prevent its oxidation by dissolved molecular oxygen. 0.2 M Standard solution of sodium carbonate was also prepared in double distilled water. The kinetics of the reaction was studied spectrophotometrically using a Systronics-118 spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 440 nm. The rate of formation of the coloured product was monitored with time.

The proposed method was used to determine α -Methyl dopa in pure and in pharmaceutical preparations. Whole tablets were crushed and ground to fine powder and dissolved to prepare test solutions of 150 ppm concentration.

Aliquots of standard solution of α -Methyl dopa were mixed with 5 ml sodium carbonate solution (0.2 M) and the time was noted. The reaction mixture was rapidly transferred into a cuvette and absorbance at 440 nm was recorded after every 15 s against a reagent blank. First absorbance was taken 1.45 min after mixing the two solutions. The procedure was repeated for different concentrations of the drug solution, with a constant concentration of sodium carbonate solution. All the experiments are carried out at room temperature (25 °C).

The regression equations of the calibration graphs were calculated using method of least squares.

Results and discussion

The reaction between the drug and sodium carbonate in water produces a yellow colour which increases with increase in time (Fig. 1) and provides a basis for kinetic study.

Fig. 1. Variation of absorbance of drug-reagent mixture with time (a) 100 ppm, (b) 200 ppm, (c) 300 ppm.

It has been reported that α -Methyl dopa is oxidized in alkaline media to a polymeric melanin like pigment³⁵ via a reaction pathway described elsewhere³⁶, similar and parallel to that of L-dopa³⁷. α -Methyl dopa in alkaline solution is first oxidized to α -Methyl dopaquinone analogous to dopaquinone in L-dopa³⁸ which gives a yellow coloured solution showing two absorption bands at 302 and 440 nm. α -Methyl dopaquinone has a very transitory existence (half life of 5 ms at 25 °C)³⁶ and evolves to leucomethyl dopachrome : which gets converted to methyl dopachrome by oxidation, then to 5,6-dihydroxy-2-methylindole by decarboxylation, then to 2-methylindole-5,6-quinone by oxidation and finally to melanoid pigment. It has been shown that the decarboxylative rearrangement of methyl dopachrome to 5,6-dihydroxy-2-methylindole is the rate limiting reaction³⁶ in the overall transformation of α -Methyl dopa to a melanin-like pigment.

Reaction-rate method :

A plot of initial rate of reaction versus concentration of the drug (Fig. 2) gives a straight line and serves as a

Fig. 2. Calibration plot of initial rate of reaction versus drug concentration.

calibration curve. The rate of reaction was calculated from the variable time method^{39,40} of measurement as $\Delta A/\Delta t$ where A is the absorbance and t is the time in seconds. In the present study $\Delta A/\Delta t$ was obtained by dividing the absorbance measured 105 s (1.45 min) after mixing the drug and the reagent solutions by 105 s, assuming that the absorbance of the coloured product at $t = 0$ is zero. The regression equation for the reaction rate versus concentration graph is

$$\text{Rate} = 2.13 \times 10^{-4} + 0.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ drug conc. (ppm)},$$

$$r^2 = 0.999$$

A plot of log of reaction rate versus log of drug concentration gives a straight line (Fig. 3) which shows that the

Fig. 3. Plot of log of reaction rate versus log of drug concentration (mol/L).

reaction rate of the drug obeys the following equation.

$$\text{Rate} = K' [\text{drug}]^n \quad (1)$$

where K' is the rate constant and n is the order of the reaction.

Taking logarithms of eq. (1)

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{ rate} &= \log K' + n \log [\text{drug}] \\ \log \Delta A/\Delta t &= \log K' + n \log [\text{drug}] \\ &= -0.247 + 0.837 \log [\text{drug}], \\ r^2 &= 0.999 \end{aligned}$$

Thus $K' = 0.578$ and the reaction is first order ($n = 0.840$) with respect to drug concentration.

Fixed absorbance method :

The change in absorbance with time was followed for different concentrations of the drug. A fixed value of absorbance was arbitrarily selected and the time at which the absorbance was achieved was found. The reciprocal

of time ($1/t$) was plotted versus the initial concentration of the drug and linear calibration graph was obtained. Fig. 4 shows calibration graphs at different fixed absorbances (selected arbitrarily). The regression equations for calibration graphs corresponding to different fixed absorbances are given in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Calibration plots of inverse of time versus drug concentration at fixed absorbance : (a) $A = 0.248$, (b) $A = 0.280$, (c) $A = 291$.

Table 1. Regression equations for the reaction rate method, fixed absorbance method and fixed time method for the determination of α -Methyl dopa

Method	Regression equation	r^2
Reaction rate method	Rate = $2.13 \times 10^{-4} + 0.7 \times 10^{-5} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.999
Fixed absorbance method		
Fixed absorbance, A		
0.248	$1/t = -0.193 \times 10^{-3} + 0.32 \times 10^{-4} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.996
0.280	$1/t = -0.173 \times 10^{-3} + 0.26 \times 10^{-4} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.998
0.291	$1/t = -0.205 \times 10^{-3} + 0.24 \times 10^{-4} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.997
Fixed time method		
Fixed time (s)		
105	$A = 0.0223 + 0.750 \times 10^{-3} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.999
120	$A = 0.0313 + 0.797 \times 10^{-3} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.999
135	$A = 0.0391 + 0.841 \times 10^{-3} \times \text{drug conc. (ppm)}$	0.999

t = time in seconds and A = absorbance.

Fixed time method :

Change in absorbance with time was followed for different concentrations of the drug. At a fixed time, which

was accurately determined, the absorbance was measured. Calibration graphs of absorbance versus initial concentration of the drug at fixed times of 105, 120 and 135 s were drawn (Fig. 5). Correlation coefficients of the curves were calculated. The regression equations for the calibration graphs corresponding to different fixed times are given in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Calibration plots of absorbance versus drug concentration at fixed time : (a) 105 s, (b) 120 s, (c) 135 s.

Several different methods were tried to construct calibration curves for the determination of the drug from the rate data : initial rate of reaction, the fixed absorbance and the fixed time methods. As seen, excellent calibration curves were obtained with all the three methods. Regression equations were calculated for every calibration curve. It is evident that in every method there is an excellent correlation between the analytical parameter and the concentration of the drug; in fixed time and reaction rate methods the correlation coefficient is 0.999 and hence, these are the most suitable methods for the assay of the drug. The above methods were performed in the concentration range of 25–300 ppm.

The applicability of the proposed method was evaluated by measuring 5 independent samples of α -Methyldopa in pure form at three different concentrations viz. 100, 150 and 200 ppm, and in pharmaceutical preparations (tablet form) at 150 ppm drug concentration. The standard deviation, the percent standard deviation and the percent recovery results are given in Tables 2 and 3. The percent recovery has been 98.340 to 100.034 and the RSD(%) from 0.45 to 0.99 which can be considered to be very satisfactory and thus the proposed methods are very effective for the determination of α -Methyldopa in pure and in pharmaceutical formulations.

Table 2. Results of the determination of α -Methyldopa in pure form by the proposed methods

Method	Amount taken (ppm)	Amount ^a found (ppm)	%Recovery	SD	RSD (%)
Reaction rate method	100	100.034	100.034	0.51	0.51
	150	148.945	99.296	0.83	0.56
	200	198.494	99.247	1.21	0.61
Fixed absorbance method	100	98.543	98.543	0.75	0.75
	150	148.009	98.673	1.84	0.92
	200	197.761	98.881	1.66	0.83
Fixed time method	100	98.065	99.065	0.93	0.74
	150	149.420	99.613	0.96	0.48
	200	199.123	99.561	1.30	0.65

^aAn average of six determinations.

Table 3. Results of the determination of α -Methyldopa in pharmaceutical preparations (in tablet form) by the proposed methods

Method	Amount taken (ppm)	Amount ^a found (ppm)	%Recovery	SD	RSD (%)
Reaction rate method	150	149.33	99.553	0.91	0.61
Fixed absorbance method	150	147.51	98.340	1.66	0.99
Fixed time method	150	149.12	99.413	0.67	0.45

^aAn average of six determinations.

Conclusion :

The proposed method is simple which precludes any use of harmful and costly organic solvents and reagents. Other than water the only reagent used is sodium carbonate, which is not only cheap and safe but is available in any analytical laboratory with excellent shelf life. The procedure of the proposed method is simple and time saving because only one-step reaction is involved and no elaborate treatment. No tedious procedures, extractions, multiple step reactions, heating and standing times etc. are involved. The proposed method is accurate and reproducible, and requires simple apparatus for its performance, and consequently is suitable for routine quality control of the drug.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Director, University Science Instrumentation Centre and Head, Department of Chemistry for providing facilities.

References

1. J. A. Oates, L. Gillespie, S. Udenfriend and A. Sjoerdsma, *Science*, 1960, **131**, 1890.
2. K. S. Marshall and N. Castagnoli, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, **16**, 266.
3. L. M. Nelson and M. Carruthers, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1980, **183**, 295.
4. G. P. Jackman, V. J. Carson, A. Bobik and H. Skews, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1980, **182**, 277.
5. J. Wagner, M. Palfreyman and M. Zraika, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1979, **164**, 41.
6. K. Rona, K. Ary, B. Gachalyi and I. Klebovich, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1996, **730**, 125.
7. H. K. Jeon, H. Nohta, K. Ohtsubo and Y. Ohkura, *Anal. Sci.*, 1989, **5**, 663.
8. The United States Pharmacopoeial Convention, 2000, Rockville, MD, The United States Pharmacopoeia 24th edn., The National Formulary 19.
9. D. Amin, *Analyst*, 1986, **111**, 255.
10. M. I. Walash, A. AbouOuf and F. B. Salem, *J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.*, 1982, **65**, 1445.
11. W. I. Mohamed and F. B. Salem, *Anal. Lett.*, 1984, **17**, 191.
12. F. B. Salem, *Talanta*, 1987, **34**, 810.
13. F. B. Salem, *Anal. Lett.*, 1993, **26**, 1959.
14. S. S. Badawy, Y. M. Issa and A. S. Tag-Eldin, *Electroanalysis*, 1996, **8**, 1060.
15. S. Ozkan and I. Biryol, *FABAD Farm. Bilimler. Derg.*, 1990, **15**, 97.
16. M. E. Garrido, J. L. F. C. Lima and C. Delerue-Mattos, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1997, **15**, 845.
17. A. Mohammadi, A. B. Moghaddam, R. Dinarvand, J. Badraghi, F. Atyabi and A. K. Saboury, *Intl. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2008, **3**, 1248.
18. M. Tubino, D. Batista and J. A. Rodrigues, *Anal. Lett.*, 2006, **39**, 327.
19. E. A. Gadkariem, K. E. E. Ibrahim, N. A. A. Kamil, M. E. M. Haga and H. A. El-Obeid, *Saudi Pharmaceut. J.*, 2009, **17**, 303.
20. N. A. El-Rabbat and N. M. Omar, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1978, **67**, 779.
21. L. Zivanovic, S. Vasiljevic and D. Radulovic, *Boll. Chim. Farm.*, 1991, **130**, 162.
22. P. Nagaraja, R. A. Vasantha, K. C. S. Murthy and K. S. Rangappa, *Chemia Analytyczna*, 2001, **46**, 569.
23. P. B. Issopoulos, *Frenesius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1990, **336**, 124.
24. T. Aman, I. U. Khan, N. Aslam and I. Ahmed, *Anal. Lett.*, 1998, **31**, 1007.
25. J. J. B. Nevado, J. M. L. Gallego and P. B. Laguna, *Frenesius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1995, **353**, 21.
26. P. Nagaraja, K. C. S. Murthy, K. S. Rangappa and N. M. M. Gowda, *Talanta*, 1998, **46**, 39.
27. I. C. Vieira and O. Fatibello-Filho, *Talanta*, 1998, **46**, 559.
28. P. B. Issopoulos and P. T. Economou, *Farmaco.*, 1993, **48**, 127.
29. M. I. Walash, A. AbouOuf and F. B. Salem, *J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.*, 1985, **68**, 91.
30. P. Nagaraja, R. A. Vasantha and K. R. Sunitha, *Talanta*, 2001, **55**, 1039.
31. P. B. Issopoulos, *Pharm. Acta Helv.*, 1989, **64**, 82.
32. G. P. Haight and V. Paragamian, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 642.
33. G. R. Rao, S. Raghuvver and P. Khadgapathi, *Indian Drugs*, 1985, **2**, 559.
34. P. R. S. Ribeiro, I. Pezza and H. R. Pezza, *Eclética Quimica.*, 2005, **30**, 23.
35. R. Sasseti and H. Fudenberg, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1971, **20**, 57.
36. T. E. Young, B. W. Babbit and L. A. Wolfe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **45**, 2899.
37. T. E. Young, J. R. Griswold and M. H. Hulbert, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 1980.
38. B. A. Hassan, K. D. Khalaf and M. D. Guardia, *Talanta*, 1995, **42**, 627.
39. D. Persez-Bendito and M. Silva (eds.), "Kinetic Methods in Analytical Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1988, Ch. 11, pp. 44.
40. A. Martin (ed.), "Physical Pharmacy", 4th ed., Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, PA, 1993, pp. 287.

